

PRIVATE AND PUBLIC GOODS

Goods are classified based on their consumption characteristics, particularly rivalry (whether consumption by one reduces availability for others) and excludability (whether people can be prevented from using them). It can be classified into four categories: private goods, public goods, common goods, and club goods.

An important characteristic of private and public goods is that they can be distinguished in terms of rivalry and excludability.

A rival good is a good which can be consumed or possessed by a single user only without the interference of another while, a non-rival good can be consumed or possessed by multiple users, e.g internet, radio, etc. Non-excludable goods are public goods that cannot exclude a certain individual or group of individuals from using them. It cannot prevent non-paying individuals from enjoying the benefits of a good, product or service, e.g., public roads.

Balancing public and private goods provision is essential for sustainable and equitable economic development.

Private Goods can be defined as goods that are rival and excludable. A person's consumption reduces the quantity available for others and only those who have paid for the goods or service can make use of it. This includes food, clothing, cars, and personal gadgets.

In the case of food, it is a classic example of a private good because it is rivalrous that is, consumption by one person reduces the amount available for others, e.g. If a fruit is eaten, that unit of fruit cannot be consumed by another. When one person consumes a unit of food (e.g., an apple or a sandwich), that particular unit is no longer available for others to consume. In other words, consumption by one person reduces the availability of the good for others. It is also excludable because it is possible to prevent others from consuming the same food, e.g., Putting mechanisms such as ownership, pricing, or exclusive access on a good or commodity can exclude others from consuming the good.

Public Goods, on the other hand means goods that are non-rival and non-excludable. A person's consumption doesn't reduce availability for others and it is usually difficult to exclude non-payers from benefiting. Examples are national defense, street lighting, clean air, and public parks etc.

National defense is a classic example of a public good because it benefits everyone in a society. It is non-rivalrous, meaning one person's consumption does not reduce the availability of the good for others, the protection it provides is not diminished by the fact that one person is benefiting from it. It forces benefits on everyone in the nation collectively because the consumption of defense by one person (or region) does not diminish the protection available to others.

It is also difficult to exclude individuals from the defense provided by a nation meaning it is difficult or costly to exclude individuals from benefiting, even if they do not pay for the good. It is challenging or impractical to exclude individuals from the benefits of national defense, regardless of whether they contribute financially to its provision.

The non-rivalrous and non-excludable nature of national defense makes it a classic example of a public good. Because of these characteristics, there is a collective action problem that individuals may benefit from national defense even if they don't contribute to its funding, leading to the potential under-provision of defense in a purely market-driven system.

Economists and decision-makers can better grasp how various things should be funded and managed thanks to this categorization. Usually, the market provides private commodities, and consumers pay for the things they use. On the other hand, public goods frequently need government involvement or some kind of collective action because the market may not be able to supply them effectively because of the free-rider problem, which occurs when some gain without paying, and the challenge of keeping out non-payers.

The free rider problem occurs when individuals or groups benefit from a good or service without contributing to its cost relying on others to bear the expense.

In summary, the classification of goods into private and public categories is based on the fundamental economic concepts of rivalry and excludability. Food, being rivalrous and excludable, falls into the category of private goods, while national defense, being non-rivalrous and non-excludable, is a classic example of a public good.